

What is known about the effectiveness, cost-effectiveness and experiences of interventions to reduce suicidality for autistic people? Protocol for a scoping review.

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Rationale

Autistic people and people with elevated autistic traits are at a higher risk of suicidality (suicidal ideation, suicide plans, suicide attempts) than the general population.¹ A clinical cohort study of newly diagnosed adults with Asperger's syndrome found that 66% reported suicidal ideation which was nine times higher than in the general population, and 35% reported plans or attempts at suicide.² A matched case-cohort study showed that autistic people are seven times more likely to attempt suicide than the general population, with autistic women twice as likely to attempt suicide than autistic men.³ Large-scale cohort studies in Sweden⁴ and Denmark⁵ reported a 2.56-fold and a 3.83-fold increase in death by suicide for autistic people compared to the general population from 1987 to 2009 and from 1995 to 2016 respectively. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis of suicidality in autistic and possibly autistic people synthesised 36 primary studies and pooled prevalence estimates for three suicidality outcomes – suicidal ideation, suicidal attempts and behaviours, and suicidal plans.¹ It found suicidal ideation was prevalent in over a third (34.2%) of autistic and possibly autistic people without co-occurring intellectual disability; suicide plans were prevalent in 21.9%, and suicide attempts and behaviours in 24.3%. These estimates are considerably higher than those in the general population (suicidal ideation – approximately 9%; suicide attempts and behaviours, and suicide plans – between 2% and 3%). A proportion of those with elevated autistic traits remain undiagnosed⁶ and a recent study identified evidence that those who died by suicide with undiagnosed possible autism were significantly higher than in the general population (41.4%).⁷

The high prevalence of suicidality has been associated with a lack of support for autistic people.^{8 9 10} The NHS Long Term Plan and Building the Right Support committed to increase the availability and accessibility of community mental health support, including crisis support, for autistic people to reduce the need for inpatient mental health care and ‘preventable deaths’.^{11 12} Despite these commitments to reduce avoidable mortality and improve support available in the community, there is a lack of evidence on effective interventions to treat suicidality, with autistic people reporting that they receive interventions that have been designed for other groups and are inappropriate for their needs.^{13 14} Qualitative evidence from autistic people’s experiences of suicidality interventions highlights their desire for interventions that are tailored to their individual needs.⁸

The Department of Health & Social Care (DHSC) identified autistic people as a key group of concern in the National Suicide Prevention Strategy for England¹⁵ and committed to building the evidence on preventing suicidality for autistic people in order to develop evidence-based policy and guidance. DHSC commissioned the University of Exeter Policy Research Programme Evidence Review Facility to undertake a scoping review of the peer reviewed academic literature on interventions for autistic people experiencing suicidality to inform a decision on commissioning primary research to test interventions with autistic people, in part fulfilment of the National Suicide Prevention Strategy.¹⁵

Aim

To undertake a scoping review to better understand the quantity and nature of existing primary research evaluating interventions to support autistic people experiencing suicidality.

Methods

The methods for this scoping review are informed by Arksey and O’Malley’s¹⁶ scoping review methodology and Levac et al’s¹⁷ methodological enhancement. According to this framework, there are six stages to undertaking a scoping review: (i) identifying the research question; (ii) identifying the relevant studies; (iii) study selection; (iv) charting of the data; (v), collation, summarising and reporting the results; and (vi) consultation.^{16 17}

Research question

What is the quantity, range and nature of studies on the effectiveness, cost-effectiveness and experiences of interventions to reduce suicidality for autistic people?

Identification of studies

The search strategy will be developed by an information specialist (SB) in consultation with the review team and stakeholders. The bibliographic database search strategy will include both free-text

searching (i.e. title and abstract searching) and indexing terms (e.g. MeSH in MEDLINE) and will combine search terms for autism with search terms for suicidality or self-harm. We will search the following bibliographic databases:

CENTRAL (via the Cochrane Library)

CINAHL (via EBSCO)

Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Science (CPCI-S) (Web of Science)

EconLit (via EBSCO)

MEDLINE (via Ovid)

PsycInfo (via Ovid)

Search results will be exported to Endnote 21 and de-duplicated using the automated de-duplication function and manual checking. No date limits will be applied except for in the Conference Proceedings Citation Index, which we will limit to the last three years to identify abstracts on emerging research which is not yet published in journal article format.

Backwards citation chasing will be conducted on studies meeting review inclusion criteria. We will also review reference lists of relevant reviews and search a selection of topically relevant websites, including Autistica.org.uk, consulting with stakeholders on other relevant websites to search. Finally, we will search for unpublished trials via ClinicalTrials.gov and the WHO clinical trials registry (ICTRP) and contact individuals conducting research in this field to see if they are aware of published or unpublished studies which are in progress or have been completed which meet the inclusion criteria.

Study selection

Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria to be applied to the studies identified through the search strategy are detailed below. We have organised the criteria according to the SPIDER format²⁰ which is a qualitative/mixed-method studies framework and stands for Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation and Design.

Sample

Include:

- Autistic people (adults, children and young people) who have received a diagnosis of autism/Aspergers syndrome.

- People (adults, children and young people) who are possibly autistic (i.e. individuals who score highly on measures of autistic traits but do not have a diagnosis).
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Exclude:

- People, including children and young people, who do not have a confirmed autism diagnosis or have not been identified as possibly autistic.

Phenomenon of interest

Defining autism

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is defined as a disorder characterised by marked impairments in social interaction and communication accompanied by a pattern of repetitive, stereotyped behaviours and activities. Developmental delays in social interaction and language surface prior to age three years.¹⁸ ASD can be co-diagnosed with certain genetic conditions: “Single gene disorders which include both autosomal and X-linked defects associated with autism as a feature include tuberous sclerosis (TSC1 and TSC2 genes), neurofibromatosis (NF1 and NF2 genes), X-linked Rett (MECP2 gene) and fragile X (FMR1 gene) syndromes.”¹⁹

Defining suicidality

Suicidality is defined, for the purpose of this scoping review, as any suicidal thoughts and behaviours, such as suicidal ideation, suicidal intent and attempted suicide that, without intervention, place someone at high risk for mental health crisis or suicide (after Newell et al, 2023). Self-harming behaviours will be included however they present within the autistic person.

- Any intervention intended to reduce suicidality in autistic people. This also includes assessment-related interventions which evaluate strategies to identify autistic people with suicidality, for example.
- Any intervention evaluated for feasibility and acceptability in reducing suicidality in autistic people (includes implementation).
- Any intervention intended to reduce suicidality evaluated for cost-effectiveness.
- Experiences of patients and the people who support them of interventions to reduce suicidality (e.g. process evaluations).
- Attitudes and perceptions of patients and people who support them on the design of interventions to reduce suicidality.

Exclude:

- Any intervention not aimed at reducing suicidality in autistic people.
- Any intervention to develop and validate assessment tools to identify suicidality in autistic people.
- Studies exploring the relationship between personal characteristics of people with autism and suicidal behaviour.

Design

Include:

- Randomised controlled trials.
- Controlled trials.
- Prospective and retrospective cohort studies.
- Before and after studies.
- Modelling studies.
- Qualitative studies/process evaluations (based on interview and survey data).
- Feasibility studies (including those with no comparator).
- Research protocols.
- Conference abstracts.

Exclude:

- Epidemiological studies.
- Case studies.
- Systematic, scoping or narrative reviews.
- Letters, editorials, discussion pieces.

If necessary, we will further limit study design eligibility in order to include the most relevant and robust evidence within the review.

Evaluation

Include:

- Studies where the outcome measure tested is a reduction in attempted suicides, completed suicides or suicidal thoughts and behaviour in autistic people.
- Studies that explore experiences of interventions to reduce suicidality in autistic people.
- Studies that explore attitudes and perceptions on the design of interventions to reduce suicidality in autistic people.

Research type

Include

- Primary research i.e. quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods.

Date limit:

None.

Geographical limit:

None.

Language restriction:

Studies published in English only.

Process of applying inclusion criteria

As an initial calibration exercise of inclusion judgments and the clarity of our inclusion criteria, all reviewers will apply inclusion and exclusion criteria to the same sample (n=100) of search results. Decisions will be discussed in a group meeting to ensure consistent application of criteria. Where necessary, inclusion and exclusion criteria will be revised to enable more consistent reviewer interpretation and judgement. The revised inclusion and exclusion criteria will then be applied to the title and abstract of each identified citation independently by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved through discussion or referral to a third reviewer as required. The full text of each record will be assessed against the revised inclusion and exclusion criteria used to complete title and abstract screening by two reviewers independently, with disagreements resolved through discussion or referral to a third reviewer.

Endnote 20 software will be used to support record management and screening. A PRISMA-style flowchart will be produced to detail the study selection process and reason for exclusion of each record retrieved at full text will be reported.

Charting the data

A standardised data extraction coding set will be developed and piloted by the review team on a selection of included studies and refined if needed. It will be used to collect the following information from each included full text:

- First author
- Date of publication
- Title of publication
- Study location

- Study aims and objectives
- Data collected
- Data collection method
- Data analysis performed
- Study setting
- Inclusion criteria
- Participant characteristics (age, gender, diagnosis of autism, possible autism)
- Intervention name and aim
- Intervention and comparator characteristics
- Comparator name and aim
- All outcomes assessed in study
- Evidence relating to effectiveness and economic effectiveness
- Evidence relating to experiences of, attitudes and perceptions on, interventions or designed interventions to reduce suicidality
- Summary of key findings (based on paper abstract)

Data extraction will be performed by one reviewer and checked by a second, with disagreements being settled through discussion, recruiting a third person as arbiter, if required.

Study quality assessment strategy

Although quality assessment does not generally form part of the scoping study remit,^{16 21} the quality of studies selected for inclusion may be appraised using a suitable tool, if time and resources allow. All assessments will be performed by one reviewer and checked by a second, with disagreements settled by a third reviewer if necessary.

Collation, summarising and reporting of the results

Data from the included studies will initially be tabulated and summarised narratively. A numerical analysis will provide an overview of the quantity and nature of the evidence. An analytical framework or grid will be developed to provide an overview of the breadth of the evidence and studies with similar intervention characteristics and settings synthesised narratively. Studies that evaluate self-harm reduction interventions will be considered separately.

Policy Relevance

This review was requested by stakeholders from DHSC and NHS England and will be used to identify gaps in the existing literature and inform decision-making on commissioning of future primary research.

Consultation

Our stakeholders have been instrumental in determining the aims and scope of the review. Thus far, they have been involved with the identification of the review's research question and development of the review protocol. This involvement will continue throughout the review and involve:

- Commenting on search strategy
- Commenting on relevance of included studies;
- Commenting on final data extraction form;
- Providing feedback on preliminary results;
- Commenting on draft report;
- Supporting dissemination of findings.

Patient and public involvement

We will seek to involve patients and members of the public in the conduct of this scoping review by drawing upon the experience of our patient and public involvement group. Key areas for integrating their feedback during the review process include:

- Commenting on the project protocol;
- Checking what level of information will be useful to the intended users of our review;
- Ensuring our review of available evidence is accessible to our intended audience;
- Providing feedback on preliminary findings and draft reports;
- Identifying opportunities for dissemination of findings.

Dissemination plans

We will produce a final project report which will be sent to our key stakeholders. The results from this review will be published within relevant academic journals. We will also produce plain language summaries with our PPI group, which can then be used as a basis for other dissemination materials the research and stakeholder team feel are appropriate. These dissemination materials may include a Briefing paper, podcast and blog post. Key outputs will be shared via the Exeter PRP ERF webpage, blog and Twitter feed.

The dissemination plan will be developed further as the findings of the review emerge to allow for the key messages and delivery mechanisms for each audience to be identified.

Resources

The estimated timeline is a minimum of 3.5 months, based on the part of the team working full time on this review.

This review will include input from all members of the Exeter Policy Research Programme Evidence Review Facility. We will also seek to consult with review stakeholders, patients and members of the public at key stages throughout the review process, as detailed in the 'Stakeholder involvement' section above.

References

1. Newell V, Phillips L, Jones C, Townsend E, Richards C, Cassidy S. A systematic review and meta-analysis of suicidality in autistic and possibly autistic people without co-occurring intellectual disability. *Molecular autism*. 2023;14(1):12.
2. Cassidy S, Bradley P, Robinson J, Allison C, McHugh M, Baron-Cohen S. Suicidal ideation and suicide plans or attempts in adults with Asperger's syndrome attending a specialist diagnostic clinic: a clinical cohort study. *The Lancet Psychiatry*. 2014;1(2):142-7.
3. Hirvikoski T, Boman M, Chen Q, D'Onofrio B, Mittendorfer-Rutz E, Lichtenstein P, et al. Individual risk and familial liability for suicide attempt and suicide in autism: a population-based study. *Psychological Medicine*. 2020;50(9):1463-74.
4. Hirvikoski T, Mittendorfer-Rutz E, Boman M, Larsson H, Lichtenstein P, Bölte S. Premature mortality in autism spectrum disorder. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*. 2016;208(3):232-8.
5. Kølves K, Fitzgerald C, Nordentoft M, Wood SJ, Erlangsen A. Assessment of suicidal behaviors among individuals with autism spectrum disorder in Denmark. *JAMA Network Open*. 2021;4(1):e2033565-e.
6. Richards G, Kenny R, Griffiths S, Allison C, Mosse D, Holt R, et al. Autistic traits in adults who have attempted suicide. *Molecular Autism*. 2019;10:1-10.
7. Cassidy S, Au-Yeung S, Robertson A, Cogger-Ward H, Richards G, Allison C, et al. Autism and autistic traits in those who died by suicide in England. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*. 2022;221(5):683-91.
8. Camm-Crosbie L, Bradley L, Shaw R, Baron-Cohen S, Cassidy S. 'People like me don't get support': Autistic adults' experiences of support and treatment for mental health difficulties, self-injury and suicidality. *Autism*. 2019;23(6):1431-41.
9. Cassidy S, Bradley L, Shaw R, Baron-Cohen S. Risk markers for suicidality in autistic adults. *Molecular Autism*. 2018;9:1-14.
10. Hedley D, Uljarević M, Wilmot M, Richdale A, Dissanayake C. Brief report: Social support, depression and suicidal ideation in adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*. 2017;47:3669-77.
11. NHS England Building the right support 2015.
12. NHS. NHS Long Term Plan 2019.
13. International Society for Autism Research. Autism Community Priorities for Suicide Prevention: An International Society for Autism Research Policy Brief. 2021.
14. Cassidy S, Cogger-Ward, H., Robertson, A. E., Goodwin, J., and Rodgers, J. Where do we go from here? Autism community priorities for future suicide research. 2021.

15. Department of Health & Social Care. Suicide prevention strategy for England: 2023 to 2028.
16. Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*. 2005;8(1):19-32.
17. Levac D, Colquhoun H, O'Brien KK. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. *Implementation Science*. 2010;5:1-9.
18. ICD-10-CM Diagnosis Code F84.0 <https://www.icd10data.com/ICD10CM/Codes/F01-F99/F80-F89/F84-/F84.0#:~:text=Billable%2FSpecific%20Code-,F84.,ICD%2D10%2DCM%20F84.>
19. Genovese A, Butler MG. The autism spectrum: behavioral, psychiatric and genetic associations. *Genes*. 2023;14(3):677.
20. Cooke A, Smith D, Booth A. Beyond PICO: the SPIDER tool for qualitative evidence synthesis. *Qualitative Health Research*. 2012;22(10):1435-43.
21. Campbell F, Tricco AC, Munn Z, Pollock D, Saran A, Sutton A, et al. Mapping reviews, scoping reviews, and evidence and gap maps (EGMs): the same but different—the “Big Picture” review family. *Systematic Reviews*. 2023;12(1):45.

Appendix 1. Ovid MEDLINE search

1. (autis* or asperg* or "pervasive development* disorder*" or "high functioning" or asc or asd).tw.
2. exp Autism Spectrum Disorder/
3. Child Development Disorders, Pervasive/
4. or/1-3
5. (suicid* or parasuicid* or automutilation*).tw.
6. (self adj2 (harm* or injur*)).tw.
7. exp Self-Injurious Behavior/
8. or/5-7
9. 4 and 8